

Educational Policies: “Issues and Challenges in Implementation”

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine the effectiveness of educational policies and analyses the issues and challenges encountered in implementing educational in these institutions. This study's research design used a mixed method research strategy, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis methodologies. This study has obtained a wide variety of data that can be examined using descriptive statistics and thematic analysis by combining the survey technique for quantitative data collection with in-depth interviews for qualitative data collection. The quantitative study conducts a thorough evaluation of the information provided by 339 respondents who are affiliated with higher education institutions. It explores implementation, obstacles, and other facets of educational policy. The quantitative analysis reveals respondent viewpoints on subjects including standardized testing, resource limitations, and vocational education through frequencies, percentages, and descriptive data. The results support earlier studies and highlight the need for sensible, flexible strategies that deal with practical issues. Communication, stakeholder participation, policy flexibility, and alignment with institutional requirements all stand out as essential components. A critical need arises for a comprehensive and collaborative approach involving policymakers, academic leaders, and faculty members to reevaluate and refine existing educational policies. The government should focus on enhancing collaboration between stakeholders, such as policymakers, educational administrators, faculty members, and students, to foster a more coordinated effort toward policy execution.

Keywords: Educational policy, higher education institutions (HEIs), implementation, Karachi, Pakistan

1. Introduction:

Educational policy refers to a set of principles, guidelines, and rules formulated by educational authorities or governments to regulate and guide the education system within a country or region. It serves as a framework for decision-making and provides direction for

educational institutions, educators, students, and other stakeholders involved in the field of education (Zhang et al., 2022). Educational policies encompass various aspects of the education system, including curriculum development, teaching methodologies, assessment methods, resource allocation, infrastructure development, teacher training, student support services, and educational standards. These policies are designed to ensure quality education, address societal needs, promote equal opportunities, and foster the overall development of individuals (O'Farrell et al., 2023).

The development of educational policies involves a comprehensive analysis of the existing educational landscape, identification of educational goals and objectives, consideration of research and evidence-based practices, consultation with experts and stakeholders, and taking into account the social, cultural, economic, and political context of the region (Malin & Tan, 2022). Educational policies play a crucial role in shaping the education system, influencing teaching, and learning practices, and determining the educational outcomes of students. They aim to create a conducive environment for learning, enhance educational access and equity, improve educational standards, and respond to the evolving needs of society and the economy (Costa et al., 2022). Educational policies must be periodically reviewed, updated, and aligned with the changing educational landscape, technological advancements, and the education system's emerging challenges. Implementing effective educational policies requires collaboration and coordination among various stakeholders, including educational institutions, policymakers, teachers, parents, students, and community members (Lenhoff et al., 2022).

2. Literature Review

The history of educational policies in Pakistan can be traced back to the country's independence in 1947. The government recognized the importance of education for the development and progress of the newly formed nation and made efforts to establish a comprehensive education system (Zia-ur-Rehman et al., 2022). In the early years, the emphasis was on expanding access to education and providing basic literacy skills to the population. The 1959 Education Policy focused on universal primary education and aimed to increase enrolment rates. During this period, the government also encouraged private-sector participation in education (Gulshan, 2022). In the 1960s, the government introduced the National Education Commission (NEC) to address the challenges faced by the education sector. The NEC formulated policies and recommendations to improve the quality and relevance of education. The 1970s saw the nationalization of educational institutions, with the government taking control of private schools and colleges (Zia-ur-Rehman et al., 2022). In the 1980s, there was a shift towards Islamization of education, and efforts were made to incorporate Islamic teachings and values into the curriculum. The introduction of the Federal Board of Intermediate and Secondary Education (FBISE) and Aga Khan University signaled a focus on educational standards and professionalism (Ahmad et al., 2022). In the early 2000s, the government launched the National Education Policy 1998-2010 to address the challenges of access, quality, and relevance. Efforts were made to improve infrastructure, teacher training, and curriculum development (Akhtar et al., 2022).

In recent years, there has been a focus on education for all, with initiatives to increase enrollment and reduce gender disparities. The government has also aimed to improve the

quality of education through curriculum reforms, teacher training programs, and the introduction of standardized testing. It is worth noting that Pakistan's education system continues to face challenges such as inadequate funding, limited access to quality education in rural areas, gender disparities, outdated curricula, and a lack of educational infrastructure. Efforts are ongoing to address these challenges and formulate policies that can lead to a more inclusive, equitable, and quality education system in Pakistan (Samra Bashir et al., 2022). The current educational policy in Pakistan is the National Education Policy (NEP) 2021-2030. The federal cabinet approved the NEP 2021-2030 in March 2021, and it aims to bring about comprehensive reforms in the education system of Pakistan (Zia-ur-Rehman et al., 2022). The NEP 2021-2030 envisions a holistic and inclusive education system that focuses on the overall development of learners, promotes critical thinking and problem-solving skills, and prepares students to be responsible and productive citizens. The successful implementation of the policy requires collaboration and coordination among federal and provincial governments, educational institutions, teachers, parents, and other stakeholders involved in the education sector (Shah et al., 2022). The federal government of Pakistan and provincial governments collaborate to formulate and implement educational policies for HEIs, aiming to create an enabling environment for quality higher education, research, and innovation (Ali et al., 2022a; Iqbal & Ashraf, 2023).

03 Statement of the problem

There are several practical gaps related to implementing educational policies in HEIs of Pakistan. Inadequate funding for HEIs is a significant challenge in Pakistan. Insufficient financial resources can hinder infrastructure development, research initiatives, faculty hiring, and student support services (Zia-ur-Rehman et al., 2022). Moreover, maintaining and ensuring quality standards in HEIs is a persistent challenge. It involves issues such as outdated curricula, lack of alignment with industry needs, insufficient faculty development programs, limited research opportunities, and inadequate mechanisms for internal and external quality assurance (Zia-ur-Rehman et al., 2022). Challenges may include bureaucratic hurdles, lack of autonomy, centralized decision-making processes, and limited participation of stakeholders in decision-making (Farrukh et al., 2023). Also, the recruitment and development of qualified faculty members pose challenges. Insufficient professional development opportunities, low salaries, and limited career progression pathways can affect faculty motivation and performance (Hinduja et al., 2023). The curriculum offered in HEIs may not always align with the changing demands of the job market and industry needs. This can lead to a skills gap among graduates, impacting their employability. Effective coordination and collaboration among various stakeholders, including the government, HEIs, industry, and regulatory bodies, is crucial for successful policy implementation. Lack of coordination can lead to fragmented efforts, duplication of initiatives, and inefficiencies in resource allocation (Iftikhar et al., 2022).

3.1 Research Methodology

This study's research design used a mixed method strategy, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis methodologies. The study has thus employed a non-probability purposive sampling technique ([Lehdonvirta et al., 2021](#)). The study has estimated

minimum 300 responses from the sample population based on a sample-to-item ratio of 20:1 (Memon et al., 2020; Suhr, 2006) and therefore, the study has collected 339 responses from the teaching faculty of HEIs of Karachi. Moreover, the study has gathered eight in-depth open-ended face-to-face interviews from the deans and head of departments of HEIs of Karachi.

3.2. Research questions

RQ1. How effective is the current educational policy of Pakistan for HEIs of Karachi?

RQ2. What are the issues and challenges in implementing educational policies in HEIs of Karachi?

Table 3.1 Respondents' profile (n = 339)

		Frequency	Percent
Age Group	20-24 years	45	13.3
	25-29 years	47	13.9
	30-34 years	50	14.7
	35-39 years	49	14.5
	40-44 years	53	15.6
	45-49 years	47	13.9
Gender	50 years and above	48	14.2
	Male	177	52.2
Marital Status	Female	162	47.8
	Unmarried	176	51.9
Qualification	Married	163	48.1
	Bachelors	128	37.8
	Masters	111	32.7
Experience	Post-Masters	100	29.5
	1-5 years	106	31.3
	6-10 years	72	21.2
	11-15 years	83	24.5
	Above 15 years	78	23.0

Table: describes the demographics of the respondents of this study. The study included participants across different age groups: 20-24 years were 45 (13.3%), 25-29 years were 47 (13.9%), 30-34 years were 50 (14.7%), 35-39 years were 49 (14.5%), 40-44 years were 53 (15.6%), 45-49 years were 47 (13.9%), 50 years and above were 48 (14.2%). Among the respondents, 177 (52.2%) identified as male, while 162 (47.8%) were female. Regarding marital status, 176 (51.9%) were unmarried, and 163 (48.1%) were married. Educational qualifications were diverse, with 128 (37.8%) having bachelor's degrees, 111 (32.7%) holding master's degrees, and 100 (29.5%) having post-master qualifications. The participants' professional experience also varied. 106 (31.3%) had 1 to 5 years of experience, 72 (21.2%) had 6 to 10 years, 83 (24.5%) had 11 to 15 years, and 78 (23.0%) had over 15 years of professional experience.

4. Data Analysis

The research has taken descriptive analysis (for quantitative analysis) and thematic analysis (for qualitative analysis). The research study can offer a thorough analysis of both the numerical trends and patterns (quantitative) and the nuanced perspectives and experiences (qualitative) related to educational policies and their implementation in HEIs by combining descriptive analysis for quantitative data and thematic analysis for qualitative data (Schneider & Wagemann, 2010).

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Cumulative Variables	Mean	S. D.
Issues of Educational Policy	1.970	0.336
Awareness of Educational Policy	2.014	0.349
Implementation of Education Policy	1.986	0.460

The table displays the mean (average) and standard deviation (S.D.) for three cumulative variables related to educational policy. The "Awareness of Educational Policy" variable has the highest mean (2.014), suggesting that respondents, on average, possess a relatively high awareness of educational policies. The "Implementation of Education Policy" variable has a mean of 1.986, indicating respondents' moderate perception of policy implementation. Conversely, the "Issues of Educational Policy" variable has the lowest mean (1.970), implying that, on average, respondents perceive fewer challenges in educational policies. The standard deviations reveal the extent of variability from the mean: "Issues" (S.D. 0.336), "Awareness" (S.D. 0.349), and "Implementation" (S.D. 0.460). Overall, the table provides a concise overview of respondents' average perceptions and the variability in their responses regarding these policy-related dimensions.

Table 4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Issues of Educational Policy	Mean	S. D.
Using standardized tests to measure student performance and evaluate schools has both proponents and critics.	2.021	0.830
I think that limited access to resources and facilities in higher education.	1.944	0.810
I think that Insufficient funding can hinder the quality of higher education.	1.944	0.788
I think that neglecting the importance of vocational education and technical skills for career readiness.	1.959	0.791
Educational policy has limited opportunities for ongoing professional development and teaching skills.	1.982	0.842

The following table presents mean scores and standard deviations (S.D.) for specific educational policy issues. Respondents expressed a moderate sentiment (Mean: 2.021, S.D. 0.830) regarding using standardized tests to assess student performance and school

evaluation. Limited access to resources and facilities in higher education was perceived as challenging (Mean: 1.944, S.D. 0.810). Insufficient funding's impact on education quality was similarly acknowledged (Mean: 1.944, S.D. 0.788). Neglecting vocational education and technical skills for career readiness was recognized (Mean: 1.959, S.D. 0.791). Respondents also noted limited opportunities for ongoing professional development and teaching skill improvement (Mean: 1.982, S.D. 0.842). The data highlights diverse perceptions and challenges within these educational policy dimensions.

Table 4.3 Awareness of Educational Policy

		Frequency	Percent
I think that educational policy ensures that students study now to have an excellent job in the future.	Yes	111	32.7
	No	127	37.5
	May Be	101	29.8
Educational policy should focus on students' awareness of new ways to learn something.	Yes	107	31.6
	No	111	32.7
	May Be	121	35.7
Educational policy refers to the guidelines, regulations, and principles that shape and govern the educational system.	Yes	98	28.9
	No	126	37.2
	May Be	115	33.9
I think awareness of educational policies can promote transparency and accountability in the education system.	Yes	99	29.2
	No	116	34.2
	May Be	124	36.6
I think awareness of educational policies can help individuals understand the rights and entitlements of students.	Yes	121	35.7
	No	120	35.4
	May Be	98	28.9

The tabulated data captures responses regarding awareness of educational policy, presenting frequencies and corresponding percentages for each response. Regarding educational policy's influence on job prospects, 111 participants (32.7%) endorsed positive impact ("Yes"), 127 (37.5%) held opposing views ("No"), and 101 (29.8%) remained uncertain ("May Be"). Similarly, for the policy's emphasis on innovative learning methods, 107 respondents (31.6%) supported the notion ("Yes"), 111 (32.7%) contradicted it ("No"), and 121 (35.7%) had reservations ("May Be"). On defining educational policy, 98 participants (28.9%) agreed ("Yes"), 126 (37.2%) disagreed ("No"), and 115 (33.9%) expressed uncertainty ("May Be"). The role of policy in fostering transparency garnered agreement from 99 respondents (29.2%), opposition from 116 (34.2%), and uncertainty from 124 (36.6%). Lastly, 121 participants (35.7%) agreed that policy aids in understanding student rights ("Yes"), 120 (35.4%) opposed ("No"), and 98 (28.9%) were unsure ("May Be"). This data reflects multifaceted perspectives on educational policy awareness, capturing a range of opinions.

Table 4.4 Implementation of Education Policy

		Frequency	Percent
There are no clear guidelines or agreed-on instructions for effectively implementing the interdisciplinary approach.	Yes	89	26.3
	No	116	34.2
	May Be	134	39.5
I think that it is challenging to work with teachers from other disciplines.	Yes	129	38.1
	No	98	28.9
	May Be	112	33.0
I think the teaching demands, loads, and tasks, such as assessments and examinations, make it challenging to implement new ideas.	Yes	119	35.1
	No	113	33.3
	May Be	107	31.6
I think that the higher education culture and classroom environment do not support teaching through an interdisciplinary approach.	Yes	127	37.5
	No	105	31.0
	May Be	107	31.6
I think that the knowledge necessary for teaching an interdisciplinary approach.	Yes	127	37.5
	No	105	31.0
	May Be	107	31.6

The table portrays respondents' views on implementing educational policy, displaying frequencies and percentages for each response. Concerning clear guidelines for interdisciplinary implementation, 89 participants (26.3%) concurred ("Yes"), 116 (34.2%) dissented ("No"), and 134 (39.5%) were uncertain ("May Be"). Collaborating with cross-discipline educators posed challenges for 129 respondents (38.1%), while 98 (28.9%) disagreed, and 112 (33.0%) were unsure. Teaching demands as obstacles received agreement from 119 (35.1%), with 113 (33.3%) disagreement and 107 (31.6%) uncertainty. In the context of higher education culture and interdisciplinary teaching, 127 (37.5%) affirmed, 105 (31.0%) negated, and 107 (31.6%) remained uncertain. Lastly, 127 (37.5%) supported the importance of interdisciplinary knowledge, 105 (31.0%) opposed it, and 107 (31.6%) had reservations. The data underscores multifaceted viewpoints on these policy implementation aspects.

5. Recommendations

1. The study's emphasis on evaluating Pakistan's educational policies and identifying challenges to implementing these in HEIs, particularly in the context of the Theory of Constraints. By examining the challenges faced in implementing educational policies, the study contributes theoretically by highlighting specific constraints that hinder the desired improvements in HEIs (Ademovic et al., 2022). These constraints can range from infrastructural limitations to bureaucratic inefficiencies. Understanding these constraints aligns with the TOC principles of identifying the most critical limiting factors that impede

progress (Gupta et al., 2022).

2. The study's results may result in suggestions and solutions for better aligning policy design and execution. In essence, the theoretical implications of this study lie in its application of the TOC to the analysis of educational policies and their implementation challenges in HEIs of Pakistan (Amna, 2022). By identifying constraints and limitations within the context of educational policy implementation, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of how the TOC can be practically employed to address complex challenges within educational systems (Sahito et al., 2022).
3. The practical recommendations suggest that a critical and comprehensive and collaborative approach involving policymakers, academic leaders, and faculty members to reevaluate and refine existing educational policies. By fostering open dialogues and involving all stakeholders, administrators can ensure that policies align with the real-world needs of HEIs (Bocconi et al., 2022).
4. Administrators should prioritize allocating resources and infrastructural support to bridge the gaps highlighted in the study. This may involve investing in faculty development programs, modern teaching technologies, and research facilities. Such initiatives can enhance the overall quality of education and research, contributing to the effective implementation of policies (Habib, 2023).
5. The study accentuates the necessity for policies that exhibit sound macro-level formulation and possess the adaptability and contextual appropriateness required at the micro level, ensuring a seamless implementation process (Hassan, 2022).
6. The HEC should amplify its role as a catalyst for policy implementation by fostering a cooperative atmosphere among policy formulators, academia, and other invested stakeholders. Through establishing structured feedback mechanisms and platforms for ongoing dialogues, the HEC can forge arenas for collective troubleshooting and a continuous cycle of policy enhancement. This approach would render the policies more agile in the face of the ever-evolving challenges HEIs encounter (Ratner et al., 2022).
7. The government should focus on enhancing collaboration between stakeholders, such as policymakers, educational administrators, faculty members, and students, to foster a more coordinated effort toward policy execution (Zaid et al., 2022).
8. The study underscores the need for increased investment in HEIs. Adequate funding is crucial to overcoming infrastructure deficiencies, ensuring quality education, and providing opportunities for faculty development. This includes providing modern teaching and research facilities and implementing advanced technology to support effective teaching and learning (Chachar et al., 2023).
9. The study also highlights the importance of professional development for educators and administrators. Therefore, continuous training programs should be initiated to enhance their skills in curriculum design, teaching methodologies, and administrative practices. This would contribute to the overall improvement of the education system and ensure the alignment of instructional strategies with policy objectives (Farokhzadian et al., 2022).

6. Conclusion

The purpose of this study is to examine the effectiveness of the current educational policy of Pakistan in higher education institutions (HEIs) located in Karachi, as well as to identify and

analyze the issues and challenges encountered in implementing educational policies in these institutions. Collaboration amongst stakeholders, communication tactics, and policy adaptation are essential to effective implementation. The success of Pakistan's present educational strategy in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in Karachi is very important since it significantly impacts the area's socioeconomic growth, workforce readiness, and educational standards. The evaluation of policy success in this context is relevant because Karachi is one of Pakistan's key educational centers and is home to several HEIs. A nation's intellectual capital and socioeconomic development are greatly influenced by educational programs. Effective policies are crucial for Karachi's HEIs, which serve a varied student population from various socioeconomic backgrounds, to provide fair access to high-quality education. Furthermore, a country's human capital directly affects its capacity to innovate and compete globally and its global competitiveness. Effective policies are the cornerstone for promoting an atmosphere suitable for learning, promoting research, and equipping students with the skills needed by a changing labor market.

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